

DECONSOLIDATION BEHAVIOR OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS AS CORE IN SANDWICH STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

In this study, thermal-expansion treatment was made through out-of-plane direction after compression molding (so-called springback) on carbon-fiber paper reinforced thermoplastics (CPT) to investigate its deconsolidation behaviour. Spring-back is usually considered as the phenomenon to render the part useless, however, which was taken advantage on increasing the core thickness to reduce the weight of the composites. CPT was also used as core material sandwiched with unidirectional carbon fiber prepreg (UD). And the comparison was made through the different spring-back ratio and the flexural behavior of the CPT core sandwich beams. In addition, surface morphology of cross section was observed with optical microscope.

1 INTRODUCTION

When comparing with thermosetting composites, thermoplastic matrix composite is surely superior in high-cycle and complex shape molding, jointing, recycling and so on [1]. With combination of thermoplastic and discontinuous carbon fiber, the material short carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) are regarded as a promising material to mitigate environmental and energy problems because short fiber is easy to be oriented and recycled. In this study, random oriented short carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic was investigated.

When random oriented short carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic is reheated, significant thermal deformation is often observed. This phenomenon is called “deconsolidation” or “spring back” and has been reported by some researchers [2-7]. Ye et al. [2] proposed a void growth model to evaluate the degree of deconsolidation in a post-thermal operation on glass fiber-polyamide 12 composites. Wolfrath et al. [6] defined the deconsolidation as the inverse process of the impregnation and gave theoretical analyses using the knowledge of hydrodynamics. Xiao et al. [7] found the content of voids due to de-consolidation may be over 10–20% of the whole volume of the composite.

Though this kind of phenomenon is commonly unwanted in industry because it will lead to low part quality and even render parts useless due to the release of stress and high porosity, we adopted it as the method to make carbon fiber (CF) core in sandwich structure. Taking advantage of this high void content and lightweight feature, this kind of material is favorable to be applied as core in sandwich structure to achieve high stiffness-to-weight ratio.

By the analysis of the spring-back effect, the microstructure and the residual stress can be studied in the sandwich; and the methods for controlling the spring-back effect and the mechanism of the generation of residual stress are important not only in mechanical field but also in the production processes and applications.

In this study, the spring-back effect on a transversely isotropic short carbon fiber paper reinforced thermoplastic was investigated. And the sandwiches with different levels of deconsolidation were manufactured and compared under the macro measuring and observing. Meanwhile, the sandwich

made by deconsolidated carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic core was compared with foam core sandwich.

2 MATERIALS

A kind of carbon-fiber paper-reinforced thermoplastics (CPT, Awa Paper Co. Ltd.) composed of polyamide 6 (PA6) fibers and 6-mm-long carbon fibers was used. It was made through a paper-making process where short resin fibers and carbon fibers were mixed thoroughly by water and the suspension then was post-processed into paper-like substrates. This kind of CPT was used as target materials for cores in the sandwich panels. As control group, a type of foam material (Rohacell, Sunwa Trading Corporation) used in various engineering fields was applied as well.

The sandwich facings were made of unidirectional CF-PA6 prepreg (UD; CF, TR50S, Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd.; PA6, Mitsubishi Plastics Co., Ltd.) that was 132 μm in thickness.

The information of the materials used is shown as Table 1.

	CPT- PA6	UD
CF V_f [%]	23.1	54.0
Density [g/cm^3]	1.30	1.51

Table 1: The information of the materials

3 SAMPLE PREPARATION

Preliminary spring-back process was conducted. The consolidated CPT samples was put on a heated metal under 265°C without constraint. Fig. 1 shows the CPT sample before and after spring-back process. It can be clearly seen that after spring-back, CPT has uniform thickness through whole plane direction, which indicates sandwich plate with smooth surface, even uniform inner stress distribution under loading can be expected.

Figure 1: Before and after spring-back.

In panel molding, we applied spring-back process with thickness controller to obtain different deconsolidation level of CPT core. And we used two types of molding methods to fabricate the CPT core sandwich panels as shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3.

Figure 2: Method A

Figure 3: Method B

The appearances of the final products by two methods were good without any obvious deterioration and delamination as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Side view of the spring-back-core sandwich with part of core and whole facing in through-thickness direction

As for foam core sandwich, facings were molded firstly and then epoxy adhesive was used to attach the facings and core. The appearance of CPT core sandwich and foam core sandwich are shown as Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Spring-backed CPT core and foam core sandwiches

4.1 3-POINT BENDING TEST

Static 3-point bending test of the hybrid beams were performed in accordance with the ASTM D 790-03 standard. The support span-to-depth ratio of 16:1 was chosen and the width is 15 mm. The load was applied at the middle of the span through a table-top precision universal tester from Shimadzu Corporation.

4.2 3-POINT IMPACT TEST

3-point impact test was conducted by HITS-P10 high-speed puncture impact tester from Shimadzu Corporation. The test was carried out based on the standard JIS K7084.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1 THE RESULT OF 3-POINT BENDING TEST

Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 show the flexural property of spring-back-core and foam-core sandwich. Compared with conventional foam material, spring-back core can make more contribution to the mechanical performance of the sandwich.

Figure 6: The comparison of flexural modulus of the spring-back-core and foam core sandwich

Figure 7: The comparison of flexural strength of the spring-back-core and foam core sandwich

5.3 THE RESULT OF 3-POINT IMPACT TEST

When it comes to energy absorption sector, the same tendency as flexural property can also be found in the result of 3-point impact test as shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: The comparison of normalized specific energy absorption of the spring-back-core and foam core sandwich

6 CONCLUSIONS

From the experiments and results analysis, the release of the internal fiber elastic deformation regarded as the main mechanism of the spring-back effect and it contributes to the consolidation of the facing. And the CPT core sandwich shows superior to foam core sandwich in terms of mechanical property. Moreover, one-step forming process for CPT core sandwich can be considered as an efficient and reliable method when the core is designed to a suitable deconsolidation level.

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